

Social

A STUDY ON SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS AND ITS IMPACT ON THEIR ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT

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Abstract

Every human being seeks adjustment to various situations. He constantly makes efforts to adjust himself to his surroundings because a wholesome adjustment is essential for leading a happy life and going satisfaction. Social adjustment to other people is general and to the group with which they are identified is particular. The main motive of the study is to find out the social adjustment among higher secondary school students and its impact on academic achievement in Coimbatore Educational District. This research is under taken with a view to examining the relationship with social adjustment and general achievement of different high school students with a sample size 148. The investigation is analyzed by the descriptive analysis and differential analysis. The result concluded from the study that there is no substantial change with respect to mother tongue, gender, location of school, type of family, educational qualification of parents, occupation of parents, monthly income of parents in their mean score of social adjustment and academic achievement. This study might enable teachers and administrators to look for ways of enhancing social adjustment among the students from higher secondary school and its impact on their academic achievement in Coimbatore District.

Keywords: Social Adjustment; Achievement; Education; Academic.

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1. Introduction

Social adjustment defined as the variation of an individual to the social environment. Adjustment may take place by adjusting the self to the situation or by fluctuating the surroundings. (Campbell, Psychiatric Dictionary, 1996). Social adjustment as a significant sign of psychology health is a subject fascinating the consideration of many psychologists. Social growth is the most

significant feature of one's growth and it is assimilated through the relationship with others particularly with the parents, peers and the educators, and it is the measuring benchmark of social growth related to the person's adjustment with him/herself and others. The main scope of the study is the students' academic achievement can be projected on the base of the students' social adjustment and feasible solutions will be given based on the findings analyzed. This study was conducted on a sample of 148 students only. It is limited in Coimbatore District only. The hypotheses were framed to identify any significant mean score difference between gender, medium of instruction, locality, mother tongue among higher secondary school students. In addition to, to identify significant difference towards social adjustment based on the gender, medium of instruction, the location of the school, type of the school, nature of the school, type of family, educational qualification of father, educational qualification of mother, occupation of father, occupation of mother, monthly income of father and monthly income of mother.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

There are two main types of objectives undertaken by the investigator in this study work.

1.1.1. General Objectives

- To study the social adjustment among higher secondary school students and its impact on their academic achievement in Coimbatore District.
- To adopt questionnaire on social adjustment among higher secondary school students.

1.1.2. Specific Objectives

- To find out the social adjustment among higher secondary school students.
- To find out the impact of personal variables like Mother Tongue, Gender, Medium of instruction, location of the school, type of the school, nature of the school, educational qualification of father, educational qualification of mother, monthly income of father, monthly income of mother, type of family on social adjustment among higher secondary school students.

2. Research Design

The investigator adopted survey method to study on social adjustment among higher secondary school students and its impact on their academic achievement in Coimbatore district. For this study a sample of 148 from 5 various schools which are situated in and around Coimbatore district in Tamilnadu were selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique.

Table 1: Distribution of Samples based on Variables

S.NO	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1.	Mother Tongue	Tamil	119	80.4%	148
		Others	29	19.6%	
2.	Gender	Boys	110	74.3%	148
		Girls	38	25.7%	
	Location of the	Urban	82	55.4%	

3.	School	Rural	66	44.6%	148
4.	Medium of Instruction	Tamil	58	39.2%	148
		English	90	60.8%	
5.	Type of the School	Govt.	77	52%	148
		Private	71	48%	
6.	Nature of the School	Boys	52	35.1%	148
		Co-ducation	96	64.9%	
7.	Type of Family	Nuclear Family	127	85.8%	148
		Joint Family	21	14.2%	
8.	Educational Qualification of father	illiterate	11	7.4%	148
		School Level	66	44.6%	
		Diploma	26	17.6%	
		UG	33	22.3%	
		PG	11	7.4%	
		Others	1	0.7%	

9.	Educational Qualification of mother	illiterate	17	11.5%	148
		School Level	80	54.1%	
		Diploma	22	14.9%	
		UG	20	13.5%	
		PG	5	3.4%	
		Others	4	2.7%	
10.	Occupation of Father	Agriculture	13	8.8%	148
		Business	14	9.5%	
		Coolie	31	20.9%	
		Government	25	16.9%	
		Private	64	43.2%	
		Others	1	0.7%	
11.	Occupation of Mother	Agriculture	8	5.4%	148
		Business	18	12.2%	
		Coolie	23	15.5%	
		Government	23	15.5%	
		Private	23	15.5%	
		House Wife	53	35.8%	
12.	Monthly income of Father	Below Rs.20000	13	8.8%	148
		Rs.21000-Rs.30000	35	23.6%	
		Rs.31000-Rs.40000	46	31.1%	
		Above Rs.40000	54	36.5%	
13.	Monthly income of mother	Below Rs.20000	82	55.4%	148
		Rs.21000-Rs.30000	27	18.2%	
		Rs.31000-Rs.40000	20	13.5%	
		Above Rs.40000	19	12.8%	

Table 2: Scoring of Each item

S.No	Dimension	Question no.	Scoring				
			SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Social Adjustment Scale	1 to 12, 15, 16,18 to 23,25,27,28,29	5	4	3	2	1
2.	Social Adjustment Scale	13,14,17,24,26	1	2	3	4	5

Table 3: Ranks assigned for the scores

Social Adjustment	
Scores	Rank
29 to 67	Low
68 to 105	Moderate
106 to 145	High

Table 4: Ranks assigned for the Academic Achievement scores

Academic Achievement Scores	
Scores	Rank
Less than 45	Low
46 to 63	Moderate
64 to 80	High

HYPOTHESIS 1:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards social adjustment between boys and girls among higher secondary school students.

Table 5: Frequency and percentage difference towards social adjustment between boys and girls among higher secondary school students

Gender	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Boys	1	0.91	47	42.72	62	56.36	110
Girls	0	0	8	21.05	30	78.95	38

It is conclude from the Table 5 that amid the boys, 56.36% of them have high Level, 42.72% of them have moderate Level and 0.91% of them have low level of social adjustment. Similarly, amid the girls, 78.95% of them have high Level and 21.05% of them have moderate Level. The result inferred that majority of the boys and girls have high level of social adjustment. But comparatively, the girls have high level of social adjustment than the boys.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards social adjustment between Tamil and English medium among higher secondary school students.

Table 6: Frequency and percentage difference towards social adjustment between Tamil and English medium among higher secondary school students

Medium of Instruction	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Tamil	0	0	21	36.21	37	63.79	58
English	1	1.11	34	37.78	55	61.11	90

It is conclude from the Table 6 that amid the Tamil medium students, 63.79% of them have high Level and 36.21% of them have moderate Level of social adjustment. Similarly, amid the English medium students, 61.11% of them have high Level, 37.78% of them have moderate Level and 1.11% of them have low level of social adjustment. The result inferred that majority of the Tamil and English medium have high level of social adjustment. But comparatively, the Tamil medium students have high level of social adjustment than the English medium students.

HYPOTHESIS 3:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards social adjustment between the rural and urban school among higher secondary school students.

Table 7: Frequency and percentage difference towards social adjustment between the rural and urban school among higher secondary school students.

Location of the School	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Urban	1	1.22	33	40.24	48	58.54	82
Rural	0	0	22	33.33	44	66.67	66

It is conclude from the Table 7 that amid the urban school students, 58.54% of them have high Level, 40.24% of them have moderate Level and 1.22% of them have low level of social adjustment. Similarly, amid the rural school students, 66.67% of them have high Level and 33.33% of them have moderate Level of social adjustment. The result inferred that majority of the urban and rural school students have high level of social adjustment. But comparatively, the rural school students have high level of social adjustment than the urban school students.

3. Conclusion

- Majority of the boys and girls have high level of social adjustment. But comparatively, the girls have high level of social adjustment than the boys.
- Majority of the Tamil and English medium have high level of social adjustment. But comparatively, the Tamil medium students have high level of social adjustment than the English medium students.
- Majority of the urban and rural school students have high level of social adjustment. But comparatively, the rural school students have high level of social adjustment than the urban school students.

- There is no significant difference towards social adjustment based Mother Tongue, Gender, Medium of instruction, location of the school, type of the school, nature of the school, educational qualification of father, educational qualification of mother, monthly income of father, monthly income of mother, type of family.

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